

Synthesis of 2-Cyano-3-(methoxy-substituted-phenyl)acrylamides as Herbicides

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A number of α -isocyanoalkylidene¹ acetamides and α -cyanoalkylidene acetamides² have been found to be active against weeds of rice and wheat. Therefore some new acrylamides have been synthesised possessing active moieties like cyano group, amide linkage, aromatic system and heterocyclic system to study their herbicidal activity.

The reaction of 4-methoxybenzaldehyde with cyanoacetic acid in the presence of perchloric acid gave the acid **1a**. Knoevenagel condensation of 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde with cyanoacetic acid in the presence of ammonium acetate gave the acid **2a**. The acid **3a** was obtained by treating 3,4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde with cyanoacetic acid in the presence of sodium carbonate and aniline hydrochloride. These acids were reacted with

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TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-3*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	$\nu_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	$\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$
1a	155	59	3 150, 2 200, 1 650, 1 590, 960, 830, 775	—
2a	160	54	2 900, 2 200, 1 670, 1 580, 1 230, 1 020, 960, 830	—
3a	228-29	60	3 290, 2 200, 1 690, 1 495, 1 250, 1 050, 935, 820, 735	—
1b	130-32	55	3 300(NH), 2 200(C≡N), 1 650(C=O), 840 (Ar)	2.2 (3H, s, O=C-C=C-CH ₂), 3.1 (3H, s, N-CH ₂), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₂), 8.4 (1H, s, NHCO, exchanged with D ₂ O), 6.9-7.5 (1H, m, HC=C-(CN) and ArH)
1c	135-37	63	3 500, 2 200(C≡N), 1 650 (C=O)	3.85 (3H, s, OCH ₂), 1.2-2.2 (11H, m, methylenic protons of cyclohexyl), 6.7-7.5 (5H, m, HC=C-(CN) and ArH), 8.4 (1H, s, NHCO exchanged with D ₂ O)
1d	—	70	—	4.1 (3H, s, OCH ₂), 7.1 (1H, s, HC=C-(CN)), 7.5-7.7 (4H, m, ArH), 3.7 (8H, s, methylenic protons of morpholine)
2b	245	54	3 280, 2 200, 1 645, 810	4.41 (6H, s, OCH ₂), 3.3 (3H, NCH ₂), 2.4 (3H, s, O=C-C=C-CH ₂), 7.2 (1H, s, NHCO), 7.1 (1H, s, HC=C-(CN)), 7.5-7.7 (8H, m, ArH)
2c	—	57	—	1.1-2.2 (11H, m, methylenic protons), 4.0 (6H, s, OCH ₂), 6.9 (1H, s, HC=C-(CN)), 7.1 (1H, s, NHCO), 7.3-7.6 (3H, m, ArH)
2d	—	25	—	3.8 (8H, s, methylenic protons of morpholine), 4.4 (6H, s, OCH ₂), 7.0 (8H, s, CH=C-(CN)), 7.4 (3H, m, ArH)
3b	180-85	46	3 200, 2 200, 1 670	2.35 (3H, s, O=C-C=C-CH ₂), 3.25 (3H, s, NCH ₂), 6.2 (2H, s, -O-CH ₂ -O-), 6.9 (1H, s, HC=C-(CN)), 7.4-7.7 (8H, m, ArH), 8.45 (1H, s, NHCO)
3c	170-75	67	3 300, 2 190, 1 670, 810	1.0-2.1 (11H, m, methylenic protons), 6.2 (2H, s, -O-CH ₂ -O-), 7.0-7.1 (1H, s, HC=C-(CN)), 8.4 (1H, s, NHCO exchanged with D ₂ O), 7.45-7.7 (3H, m, ArH)
3d	148-50	52	2 200, 1 640, 820	3.8 (8H, s, methylenic protons of morpholine), 6.1 (2H, s, -O-CH ₂ -O-), 6.9 (1H, m, CH=C-(CN)), 7.4-7.8 (3H, m, ArH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolen-5-one, cyclohexylamine and morpholine to obtain the respective amides. Structures of the compounds (Table I) were established by ir and pmr spectral data³. The amides were tested for their herbicidal activity against three weeds of wheat, viz., *Phalaris minor*, *Asphodelus tenuifolius*, *Medicago denticulata* at four concentrations 100, 500 and 1000 ppm.

Biological activity⁴: By considering the relative activity of the compounds 1a-d, the herbicidal activity decreased in the order 1b > 1d > 1c > 1a. Out of compounds 2a-d, the herbicidal activity decreased in the order, 2d > 2b > 2a > 2c. The herbicidal activity of 3a was highest among compounds 3a-d, followed by 3d, 3c and 3b. Compound 3a completely inhibited the germination and root length of all the three weeds.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a EM 390 (90 MHz) instrument. Synthesised compounds showed satisfactory elemental analysis. Silica gel G (B. D. H.)

was used for tlc and column chromatography. Physical and spectral data were given in Table I.

Substituted acrylic-acids (1a, 2a). General procedure: To a mixture of the appropriate aldehyde (0.05 mol) and cyanoacetic acid (0.05 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (15 ml), was added perchloric acid (70%; 7.5 mol) and the mixture was kept for 96 h at 25°. The contents were then poured into ice-cold water (400 ml) and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol.

2-Cyano-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxy-1'-phenyl)acrylic acid (3a): To a solution of cyanoacetic acid (0.05 mol) in ether (50 ml), was added sodium carbonate (0.10 mol). The white solid formed was dissolved in absolute ethanol (50 ml). To it was added a mixture of concentrated HCl (2 ml), aniline hydrochloride (0.015 mol) and piperonal (0.45 mol) dissolved in absolute ethanol (100 ml). The mixture was then heated on a water-bath at 35-40° for 1 h and stirred the solution for 10 min to form sodium salt of the acid. The salt was treated with excess of dilute HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised from benzene, (60%).

2-Cyano-3-(methoxysubstituted phenyl)acrylamides (1-3). *General procedure*: A solution of phosphorus oxychloride was added dropwise to an ice-cold, well-stirred solution of the appropriate 2-cyano-substituted-phenylacrylic acid (0.01 mol), triethylamine (0.003 mol) and the required amine (0.01 mol) in dry dichloromethane (100 ml). To it was then added triethylamine (0.006 mol) in one lot. The reaction mixture was stirred for 0.5 h at 0° and further 8 h at room temperature. The completion of reaction was checked on tlc plates at regular intervals. The reaction mixture was decomposed in crushed-ice and extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 ml), washed with saturated solution of sodium carbonate (3 × 20 ml), water, hydrochloric acid (10%; 3 × 20 ml) and again with water. After drying over anhydrous calcium chloride, solvent was evaporated and the crude product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform mixture (1 : 3) as eluent.

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